

Strategy is a style of thinking, a conscious and deliberate process, an intensive implementation system, the science of insuring future success.

Pete Johnson

Strategy
2023 - 2027

INTRODUCTION

We are proud to present the new LIBER Strategy for the period 2023-2027. This five-year period promises to bring radical changes in the research landscape. The Strategy focuses on those developments where a leading role of LIBER will bring the most added value.

This strategy has been developed in consultation with international partner organisations and has been discussed with a wide range of LIBER libraries. The strategy plan is based on a vision for research libraries by 2027, consisting of:

- **Five interconnected components**
- **Twelve strategic priorities for LIBER and LIBER libraries to achieve this vision**
- **Organisational initiatives supporting the LIBER strategy 2023-2027**
- **The development process of the LIBER strategy plan.**

The strategy development has been guided by LIBER's mission and by LIBER's values.

LIBER'S MISSION

– to enable research to be world-class:

- Provide a state-of-the-art information infrastructure to LIBER institutions
- Enhance the experience of users in LIBER institutions, enriched by the facilities and services which LIBER can offer
- Promote and advocate for European libraries in all European and national fora where the voice of LIBER needs to be heard
- Develop library and information professionals who are innovative and can offer leadership to LIBER and to the national/international library community.

LIBER VALUES

– collaboration & inclusivity:

- High-quality services for all users of library and information services
- Intellectual freedom and access to scholarship
- Collaboration with campus, local, national, European, and global partners
- Stewardship of collections and institutional resources, in the most appropriate format
- Leadership, innovation, and a willingness to embrace opportunities for change
- Inclusivity, equality of opportunity and fulfilment of potential.

THREE DRIVING FACTORS IMPACTING RESEARCH LIBRARIES AND LIBER

We identified three main driving forces impacting research libraries and LIBER in the coming years.

Drive for
Openness

A drive for Openness comes from academia, the broader society, European governments, and the European Union.

New technologies
driving further digital
transformation

Artificial intelligence and other technological developments will accelerate the digital shift and profoundly affect research and scholarly communication.

Upholding
rights & values

An increasing awareness and demand by society and academia to uphold rights and values in the digital scholarly environment.

RESEARCH LIBRARIES WILL BE AFFECTED BY THESE DRIVING FORCES

- Perception of the added value of the library
- Role of the library vis-à-vis its stakeholders
- Library services (existing and to-be-developed)
- Positioning of library collections in the eyes of researchers

Against a backdrop of:

- Transformation of library organisations and related leadership skills
- Internal need for upskilling
- Possible budget constraints

THE ROLES OF LIBER WILL ALSO BE INFLUENCED BY THESE DRIVING FORCES

- Advocacy
- Collective action
- Capacity building
- Observatory of European landscape & participating in European projects

Against a backdrop of:

- Many partner organisations/NGOs with overlapping goals and constituencies
- Divergences between research libraries

LIBER'S VISION FOR RESEARCH LIBRARIES IN 2027

LIBER'S VISION: WHERE RESEARCH LIBRARIES SHOULD BE IN 2027

LIBER formulated a vision where research libraries should be in 2027 as a strategic response to the three driving forces and consists of five components:

- A. ENGAGED AND TRUSTED HUBS** By 2027, research libraries will be engaged and trusted hubs of their user communities, collaborating with each other and with local, national and international stakeholders in their role as change agents and facilitators, and driving public engagement in research.
- B. STATE-OF-THE-ART SERVICES** By 2027, research libraries will provide forward-looking, state-of-the-art services for collections, publishing and curation of information and (meta-)data. These services will be relevant to, and tailored for, user groups inside and outside academia.
- C. ADVANCING OPEN SCIENCE** By 2027, in collaboration with researchers, research libraries stimulate, facilitate, co-develop, and manage infrastructures and practices designed to take Open Science to the next level.
- D. UPHOLDING RIGHTS AND VALUES** By 2027, research libraries embody and uphold public and academic values of integrity, diversity and inclusion, inside and outside the research community.
- E. UPSKILLING THE LIBRARY WORKFORCE** By 2027, the staff of research libraries have the necessary knowledge, confidence and skills to take on the organisational and technological changes enabling the new roles and tasks of research libraries.

All components are very much interrelated. The last two components are seen as fundamental preconditions for the first three. On the next pages, each vision element is presented in more detail, together with the strategic priorities.

A. RESEARCH LIBRARIES AS ENGAGED AND TRUSTED HUBS

By 2027, research libraries will be engaged and trusted hubs of their user communities, collaborating with each other and with local, national and international stakeholders in their role as change agents and facilitators, and taking up task in public engagement in research.

LIBER'S PRIORITIES TO ACHIEVE THIS VISION ARE:

1. STIMULATING COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION

Strengthening the positioning of research libraries in the networked environment and leveraging their collaborative strength by (a) telling the 'story' of the research libraries' unique values, services and spaces, and their actual and future roles; (b) helping libraries in networking and collaborating with their stakeholders by sharing practices and convening action; and (c) continuing LIBER's advocacy efforts.

2. ADVANCING THE OPEN KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY

Stimulating research libraries to build a bridge to society, strengthen public engagement (with Citizen Science as a key element), and helping academic institutions re-define their societal role in the making and exchange of knowledge.

B. STATE-OF-THE-ART SERVICES

By 2027, research libraries will provide forward-looking, state-of-the-art services for collections, publishing, and curation of information and (meta-)data.

These services will be relevant to and tailored for user groups inside and outside academia.

LIBER'S PRIORITIES TO ACHIEVE THIS VISION ARE:

1. ORIENTATION ON SERVICE DEVELOPMENT AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES

LIBER can help with the orientation and evaluation of potential new technologies for library services and library users.

2. REVALUING AND RECONNECTING COLLECTIONS

Revaluing and reconnecting collections by

- opening up and safeguarding (born-) digital collections for future use;
- integrating collections in the workflows of researchers; and
- connecting academic heritage collections with collections of the wider GLAM sector.

C. ADVANCING OPEN SCIENCE

By 2027, in collaboration with researchers, research libraries stimulate, facilitate, co-develop and manage infrastructures and practices designed to take Open Science to the next level.

LIBER'S PRIORITIES TO ACHIEVE THIS VISION ARE:

1. INNOVATIVE ROADS TO OPEN ACCESS

Facilitating multiple, innovative roads to Open Access that establish a default setting of diverse, inclusive, and sustainable access to scholarship and research communication.

2. FAIR RESEARCH DATA BY DESIGN

Supporting and advocating the collaborative development and management of FAIR research data.

3. SHAPING AND SUPPORTING OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES AND PRACTICES

Transforming good practices into policies and policies into good practices.

4. OPENING UP ACCESS TO EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

Supporting the creation, access, and usage of Open Educational Resources.

5. RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

Partnering with academia to advance, adopt and implement responsible frameworks for research assessment.

D. UPHOLDING RIGHTS AND VALUES

By 2027, research libraries embody and uphold values of integrity, diversity and inclusion inside and outside the research community.

LIBER'S PRIORITY TO ACHIEVE THIS VISION IS:

DEVELOPING GUIDING PRINCIPLES, POLICIES AND RECOMMENDATIONS THAT UPHOLD AND EMBED THE VALUES AT THE HEART OF LIBER'S VISION FOR RESEARCH LIBRARIES

Values of academic sovereignty, Copyright, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusivity (DEI), European solidarity, integrity and transparency, privacy and user rights, and sustainability.

E. UPSKILLING THE LIBRARY WORKFORCE

By 2027, the staff of research libraries have the necessary knowledge, confidence and skills to take on the organisational and technological changes enabling the new roles and tasks of research libraries.

LIBER'S PRIORITIES TO ACHIEVE THIS VISION ARE:

1. Developing a cohesive, modular training programme for high-level and middle management library professionals to help libraries achieve their ambitions.
2. Helping libraries build competency in emerging areas of library services and operations relating to the strategic priorities of engaged and trusted hubs, state-of-the-art services, and Open Science.

BEYOND LIBER 2027 LIBER

With this strategy plan LIBER has chosen to work on an actionable strategy for the coming five-year period, as this will be a crucial period in transforming the digital environment for research and scholarly communications in an Open Science setting. The actions proposed by this strategy plan will ensure that research libraries have a crucial role in this transformation.

Beyond 2027, the research system and the scholarly communication system will continue to evolve due to new demands for and from the research system and ongoing technological developments. These ongoing changes will take place in an environment that will progressively emphasise the importance of Open Science and its benefits to society. Services of research libraries that support academics in the open making, sharing and re-use of new knowledge will be more important than ever.

The continuing transformations will change the research libraries themselves as well. LIBER stands ready to lead and support research libraries in their evolving roles, with the conviction that in the long term, research libraries will remain indispensable actors. In the final analysis, no other actor can deliver services based on the core values of trustworthiness, integrity, and inclusivity.

IMPLEMENTING THE NEW STRATEGY

Working Groups Primary units to conduct the strategic work

Working Groups are the primary units to conduct work on the LIBER strategy and can be seen as the lifeblood of the LIBER community. Normally between 10 to 15 Working Groups are simultaneously actively working on topics relating to the LIBER strategy, while engaging around 100 to 150 LIBER members.

In practice, the lifespan of Working Groups varies: some work on a topic for one or two years and then are dissolved, while others have a longer lifespan because of the continuing importance of the topic (e.g., Copyright & Legal Matters, Open Access). LIBER will maintain a flexible approach to Working Groups regarding their lifespan and will simplify its current reporting structure for Working Groups focusing on the strategic goals.

For the implementation of the new strategy, existing Working Groups will be asked to connect to one or two strategic priorities of this new strategy and make proposals for their focus under the new strategy. A process involving the existing Working Group members and other engaged LIBER participants was set up to develop plans to implement the new strategy.

Four Steering Committees coordinating the Working Groups

The Steering Committees coordinate the strategic work of the Working Groups, monitor their progress, and support the setting up of new Working Groups under the strategy plan. This coordination structure will be maintained in the strategic period 2023-2027. The number of Working Groups per Steering Committee is limited to three to four Working Groups at the same time in order to maintain a reasonable workload for the participants involved. For the new strategic period, four Steering Committees are envisaged: a Steering Committee focusing on 'Research libraries as engaged and trusted hubs', one focusing on 'State-of-the-art services', one focusing on 'Advancing Open Science' and one focusing on 'Upskilling the library workforce'. The possibility of a Steering Committee regarding 'Upholding rights and values' will be investigated in the course of 2022 (see below).

A fifth Steering Committee for 'Upholding rights and values'?

The strategic priorities regarding 'Upholding rights and values' are related to the activities of other Working Groups. What is the best manner to work on this strategic topic? Solutions might vary from integration in all Working Groups to creating separate Working Groups. To answer this question, the Executive Board has set up a process to consult the LIBER community.

GENESIS OF THE LIBER STRATEGY 2023-2027

A strategy task force was formed in 2021 with the following participants:

Jeannette Frey	President
Julien Roche	Vice-President
Heli Kautonen	Digital Skills and Services Steering Committee Chair
Birgit Schmidt	Research Infrastructure Steering Committee Chair
Giannis Tsakonas	Innovative Scholarly Communication Steering Committee Chair
Hilde van Wijngaarden	Treasurer
Anja Smit	Secretary General
Cécile Swiatek	Executive Board member
Lars Burman	Executive Board member
Astrid Verheusen	Executive Director
Roos Knigge	Operations Coordinator
Elizabeth Bethlehem	Communications Manager

The Strategy Task Force held meetings in 2021 on May 7, May 27, June 4, June 17, October 1, and October 8, and in 2022 on January 10 and January 25. The various development stages of the strategy were also discussed with the Executive Board (June 21 and October 20 in 2021) with the LIBER Office staff (June 3 and October 18 in 2021). Working Group Chairs were asked to provide input for the determination of the main driving forces in May 2021. Input from the LIBER community was sought in 2021 by a Moonshot discussion (June 11), by a Knowledge Café during the LIBER conference (June 23) and by an online strategy discussion on December 9. In 2022, the LIBER network provided further input during a roundtable discussion (May 20) and at the LIBER 2022 Knowledge Café (July 6). The Strategy 2023-2027 Framework was approved by LIBER Participants at the 2022 Meeting of Participants (July 7). The Strategy Task Force drafted the implementation plan from September to November, culminating in the launch of the Strategy which took place at the 2022 LIBER Winter Event (December 1).

In order to get specific input from national libraries, two interviews with LIBER members representing national libraries were held (see list below). The development process had two stages: in the period May – October 2021 a LIBER strategy framework was developed.

libereurope.eu

Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche
Association of European Research Libraries

In the period October 2021 – February 2022, a consultation process to receive input to the LIBER strategy framework involved LIBER participants as well as a range of partner organisations, and other European stakeholders in research took part in group discussions or in interviews (see the list below). The results of the consultation process have led to a number of adaptations to the LIBER strategy and has been immensely helpful in the development of the strategy implementation plans. The genesis of this strategy plan has been supported by Maurits van der Graaf, Pleiade Management and Consultancy, the Netherlands.

Input Stakeholder Organisations

ORGANISATION	RESPONDENTS
European stakeholders in research	
Science Europe	Lidia Borrell-Damián
LERU	Ignasi Labastida i Juan
EUA	Stephane Berghmans, Vinciane Gaillard
The Guild	Julien Chicot, Marianne Dörr, Robin Green
Coimbra Group	Emmanuelle Gardan
EOSC Association	Karel Luyben
OCLC	Titia van der Werf, Rachel Frick
EC DG RTD	Kostas Glinos, Victoria Tsoukala
EC DG Connect	Yvo Volman, Rehana Schwinninger-Ladak, Anna Ludin
Knowledge Exchange	John Doove, Bas Cordewener
National libraries	
German National Library	Frank Scholze
National Library of Sweden	Anna Lundén
Open Science partner organisations	
COAR	Kathleen Shearer
SPARC Europe	Vanessa Proudman
cOAlition S	Johan Rooryck
SCOSS	Martin Borchert
Library partner organisations	
EBLIDA	Ton van Vlimmeren
ARL	Mary Lee Kennedy
CARL	Susan Haigh
IFLA	Helen Mandl

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